

A Study of Behaviors in Using Social Networks of Corporate Personnel of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University

Wipada Chiawchan

Abstract—This study found that most corporate personnel are using social media to communicate with colleagues to make the process of working more efficient. Complete satisfaction occurred on the use of security within the University's computer network. The social network usage for communication, collaboration, entertainment and demonstrating concerns accounted for fifty percent of variance to predict interpersonal relationships of corporate personnel. This evaluation on the effectiveness of social networking involved 213 corporate personnel's. The data was collected by questionnaires. This data was analyzed by using percentage, mean, and standard deviation.

The results from the analysis and the effectiveness of using online social networks were derived from the attitude of private users and safety data within the security system. The results showed that the effectiveness on the use of an online social network for corporate personnel of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University was specifically at a good level, and the overall effects of each aspect was ($\bar{X}=3.11$).

Keywords— Behaviors, Social Media, Social Network.

I. INTRODUCTION

SOCIAL network is a website that allows you to connect with friends and family, share photos, videos, music and other personal information with either a select group of friends or a wider group of people, depending on the settings you select. Social networks like Facebook, MySpace and LinkedIn are great ways of keeping in touch with friends and family around the world as well as making new connections with people based on similar interests or professions. There are tons of different social networks that you can join – all for free [1]. Nowadays, there are IT divisions, departments, offices, and teams at different levels. Responsibilities have been divided into technical support and academic training and consultation. This expansion has exhausted a huge amount of financial and human resources. On top of that, there might be a big online program investment. For example, quite a few high institutions are using professional course management systems such as Blackboard, Desire2Learn, E-College, etc. These systems need maintenance and constant upgrades. Once a school has implemented the course management systems, it is very difficult to stop using the system [2].

Due to the popularity of smart phones more and more resulted in a paradigm shift within the mobile market of corporate customers. In recent years, the organization brings a

smart phone used to increase performance; allowing employees to work even though they are outside the company as well.

However, there are certain types of issues that must be considered in terms of safety and policies for dealing with a smart phone. Because social media is a communication tool that is both productive and counter-productive within any organization.

In particular, some of the information released to the public, cannot be recalled, and may cause collateral damage to oneself and to others within the organization.

This particular case study will explore academic and technical support within the university itself. Detailed questionnaires will be useful for the parties involved to make improvements within the organization. This will benefit the staff in the present in the future.

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- 1) To study behaviors in using Social Networks of corporate personnel of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University.
- 2) To study the use of social networks in operation of corporate personnel of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University.
- 3) To assess the efficacy and the use of online social networks.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Theories

A social networking service is a platform to build social networks or social relations among people who share interests, activities, backgrounds or real-life connections. A social network service consists of a representation of each user, known as a profile, his or her social links, and a variety of additional services. Social network sites are web-based services that allow individuals to create a public profile, to create a list of users with whom to share connections, and view and cross the connections within the system [3].

Most social network services are web-based and provide means for users to interact over the Internet, such as e-mail and instant messaging. Social network sites are varied and they incorporate new information and communication tools such as mobile connectivity, photo/video/sharing and blogging [4].

Online community services are sometimes considered as a social network service, though in a broader sense, social

network service usually means an individual-centered service whereas online community services are group-centered. Social networking sites allow users to share ideas, pictures, posts, activities, events, interests with people in their network.

Education and technology go hand in hand, with the network serving as the platform for what we call the learning Society.

It's true that optimizing the effectiveness of traditional education systems to maximize the value we can derive from them is a vital element of any strategy moving forward. But this is not enough. Learning is an activity not a place and goes beyond the school and the university; it always has.

The knowledge explosion, driven by the power of the network to connect people and spread ideas, has changed the very nature of learning. We must innovate and develop new modes of learning, both formal and informal, that meet the demands of knowledge-driven societies in this Information Age.

We need to embrace new approaches from nontraditional sources and foster truly open and collaborative partnerships between the public, private and non-profit sectors. In addition, those responsible for guiding learning must constantly move beyond their comfort zones and continually innovate to anticipate the needs of learners as the world around them changes.

People need to learn and relearn throughout their lives. Learning must increasingly focus on interdisciplinary collaboration and 21st century skills such as critical thinking and problem solving [5].

B. Methodology

This study concerns data collected from the sample used in the study were two groups: 1) Academic Officer 70 persons and 2) Operation Officer 143 persons were used in this study which 1,481 persons. The sample size was determined by using the calculation formula of Quota Random Sampling [6].

Questionnaire on the use of social networking divided into 3 sections, including the one with 8 questions. Part 2 is divided into three areas: the use of online social networks with 5 questions, the attitude of the users with 5 questions, the security of information with 5 questions and Part 3 as comments or suggestions on the use of online social networks.

The tools in this research consisted of questionnaire which the data were analyzed by using percentage, average (\bar{X}) and Standard deviation (S.D.) and Independent Sample T-Test to test the difference between the mean values obtained from two independent samples, and one-way anova to analysis of variance, and multiple comparisons to test that the average pair of different methods by Fisher's Least Significant Difference.

IV. RESULT OF THE STUDY

The study results founded that most corporate personnel have been using social network for information awareness with different aspects of knowledge and online conferences.

The average use was more than 3 hours per day. Behaviors using social networks in relation by gender, age, position,

affiliation lines, type of personnel and activities were calculated. Hypothesis testing and analysis of variance for the effects of this analysis is divided into three aspects:

The use of online social networks, the attitude of the users and the security analysis has found that Corporate Personnel of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. Overall and specifically at the high level, and considering each item found all at a high level. By sorting of the social network (\bar{X} =3.22), the attitude of the users (\bar{X} =3.06) and the Security (\bar{X} =3.11), the overall behaviors using of each aspect (\bar{X} =3.11).

The following analysis incorporates personnel of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University about behaviors in using social network as shown in the following table.

TABLE I
 THE QUANTITY OF SAMPLES USED IN THE STUDY BY GENDER, AGE, POSITION, TYPE OF PERSONNEL AND ACTIVITIES IN THE USE OF ONLINE SOCIAL NETWORKS AS POSSIBLE

Samples information	Quantity	Percentage
Gender		
Male	100	46.95
Female	113	53.05
Total	213	100.00
Age		
20-30 Years old	50	23.47
31-40 Years old	100	46.95
41-50 Years old	52	24.41
more than 50 Years old	11	5.17
Total	213	100.00
Position		
Academic Officer	70	32.87
Operation Officer	143	67.13
Total	213	100.00
Activities to use Social Network		
Follow News on Social Medias	20	9.39
Chat Online	46	21.60
Watch Movies/ Listen Music	28	13.15
Play Games Online	10	4.69
Social Network for Business	18	8.45
Shared Information or Photos	40	18.79
Use E-Mail	43	20.17
Other	8	3.76
Total	213	100.00
Frequency of use Social Network		
Everyday	102	47.89
2-3 Days per week	80	37.56
every week	20	9.39
Other	11	5.16
Total	213	100.00
Time to use Social Network		
Less than 1 hour	55	25.82
1-3 hours	72	33.80
more than 3 hours	86	40.38
Total	213	100.00

Table I found that the sample used in the study. Most of the samples are female 53.05 percent and the ages of 31-40 years or 46.95 percent that are Operation Officer 67.13 percent. Activities within the social network chat are 21.60 percent. They use social network every day. Most samples use surf the Internet over one hour per day or 40.38 percent.

Table II shows that the sample used in the study as a whole and specifically the good level (= 3.13). All levels the order is the use of online social networks (= 3.22) Security (=3.11) and the attitude of the users (= 3.06).

TABLE II
THE IMPACT OF PERSONNEL OF SUAN SUNANDHA RAJABHAT UNIVERSITY

Evaluation descriptions	Effective levels			No.
	\bar{X}	S.D.	Qualitative Average mark	
1. The use of social network	3.22	0.73	Good	1
2. The attitude of the user	3.06	0.79	Good	3
3. The security	3.11	0.73	Good	2
total	3.13	0.75	Good	

TABLE III
COMPARISON OF GENDER

Gender	N	\bar{X}	S.D.	S.E.	t	p
Male	100	15.73	2.51	0.57	0.36	0.73
Female	113	15.48	2.50	0.44		
total	213	15.58	2.48	0.35		

* Note significantly (p <0.05).

Table III shows individuals with different gender will affect the use of online social network of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. The use of online social networks are not significantly different statistically 0.05.

TABLE IV
COMPARISON OF AGE

Age	N	\bar{X}	S.D.	S.E.	t	p
20-40 Years old	150	16.04	2.32	0.34	1.02-	0.31
More than 41 Years old	63	17.25	0.95	0.47		
total	213	16.14	2.26	0.32		

* Note significantly (p <0.05).

Table IV shows individuals with different age will affect the use of online social network of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. The use of online social networks are not significantly different statistically 0.05.

TABLE V
EMPLOYEE COMPARISON

Age	N	\bar{X}	S.D.	S.E.	t	p
Academic Officer	70	15.75	2.65	0.94	0.51	0.60
Operation Officer	143	15.26	2.39	0.37		
total	213	15.34	2.42	0.34		

* Note significantly (p <0.05).

Table V shows individuals with different position will affect the use of online social network of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. The use of online social networks are not significantly different statistically 0.05.

TABLE VI
COMPARISON OF FREQUENCY

Frequency	N	\bar{X}	S.D.	S.E.	t	p
Frequency 1-2	182	16.27	2.08	0.33	0.83	0.40
Frequency 3-4	31	15.60	0.95	0.93		
total	213	16.14	2.26	0.32		

* Note significantly (p <0.05).

Table VI shows individuals with different frequency will affect the use of online social network of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. The use of online social networks are not significantly different statistically 0.05.

TABLE VII
TIME COMPARISON

Time to use Social Network	N	\bar{X}	S.D.	S.E.	t	p
Period 1-2	127	16.17	2.12	0.40	0.13	0.89
Period 3	86	16.09	2.48	0.53		
total	213	16.14	2.26	0.32		

* Note significantly (p <0.05). Period 1 represents less than 1 hour, Period 1 represents 1-3 hours, and Period 3 represents more than 3 hours.

Table VII shows individuals with different time to use social network will affect the use of online social networks of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. The use of online social networks are not significantly different statistically 0.05.

V. CONCLUSION

This study uses a sampling-specific of 213 persons. Data collection performed by the following steps: 1) The questionnaire distributed to the sample groups of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University 2) Statement of the respondents and, 3) The data was scored according to the criteria specified.

The study result found that personnel are using social networks were at a good level (= 3.22). Considering the item found that all the information is in a good level. All sort of easily communicate with others in an online social network (= 3.64). Use of social networks are convenient and fast (=3.26). Get the entertainment value (=3.22). Receive information through social network reliability (=3.08). Creating a business on social networks (= 2.94), the overall effect of using social networks (= 3.22).

The attitude towards the using social network of personnel at a good level (=3.06). And considering the item found that all the information is in a good level. All sort of Positive attitudes about knowledge (=3.26). The overall impact of applications (= 2.08), contact us for advice on how to solve the problem (= 3.06). The technology to improve and develop social networks (= 3.00), courtesy of the use of online social networks (= 2.88). And, the overall effect of the attitude of the users (= 3.06).

The security of the using social networks of personnel at a good level (=3.11). And considering the item found that all the information is in a good level. All sort of the security (=3.16). Had set a password in order to access online social networking (=3.14). Control to use the permissions correctly (=3.15), Control for use by authorized users correctly (=3.06) and remind your forgotten password (= 3.06).

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And, One-way ANOVA Analysis of personnel of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University with LSD (Fisher's Least Significant Difference) found that the comparison of the effects of the social networks of personnel in the field of social networks in Gender ,Age ,Position ,Frequency and Time to use social networks did significantly different statistically 0.05.

Therefore, The comparison of the effects of the attitude towards the using social network of personnel in the field of social networks in Gender and Age did significantly different but in Position, Frequency and Time to use social networks did not significantly different statistically 0.05.

Finally, the comparison of the effects of the security to use social networks of personnel in the field of social networks in Gender, Age and Position did not significantly different but in Frequency and Time to use social networks did significantly different statistically 0.05.

VI. DISCUSSION

Most commonly used Social Networks in Chat Online to conversation and use e-mail with a coworker and other. To liaise make their work more convenient. And, use tools to manage the information you share with friends in different groups or even have multiple online pages such as Facebook, Line, Instagram etc. Most personnel in field of computer and information technology use Cloud Computing and backup files System such as Dropbox, Google Drive etc.

The study found most of them associated with the Society of Learning. People in society have become increasingly common knowledge in various fields by joining together and work as a team using information technology to support. Have trust in the social network and colleague or friend to contacts through online social networking. The disclosure of personal information shared the attitudes that are aware of the consequences of the use of social networking media that is used in photos sharing enlightenment with others.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) Using social networks should be updated regularly and monitoring systems such as messaging. Or the post may be a virus into the system,

- 2) the attitude of the user should have a positive attitude to the world in exchange for learning in an online social network
- 3) the security should set a strong password to access the social network every time.

In addition, should use social media to communicate within the same group and the different groups. Tools in social networking such as make activities, to have a blog for comment, creation a group networking and profiles. The dissemination and knowledge about using social networks such as Training, conferences, seminars, making a handbook for using of social network, studying out of place, the preparation of this release, preparation of pamphlets or brochures, publicity through the site office. Supporting the development of personnel to make knowledgeable about using of social networks, preparing media and tools, prepare the system of Internet and the guidelines of activities.

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